

Combining MATLAB[®] Simulation with Telecommunications Instructional Modeling (TIMS[™]) in a Senior Level Communications Course

Dr. Richard J. Hartnett and Dr. Paul B. Crilly
Department of Engineering, Electrical Engineering,
U.S. Coast Guard Academy, New London, CT 06320
richard.j.hartnett@uscga.edu

Abstract— In this work we present some of our successes in combining MATLAB[®]-based simulation methods with Telecommunications Instructional Modeling (Emona-TIMS[™]) experimental methods to enhance student learning in a senior-level communications systems laboratory. While faculty have discussed the relative merits of simulation versus real experimentation in recent years, we find that combining these approaches has multiple advantages: (1) A TIMS[™] based approach (where we have chosen to use “real-world” demodulated audio from local radio stations as the local message signal) makes students feel that they are engaged in “real-world modulation/demodulation;” (2) The TIMS[™] based approach inherently reinforces a “concept map” (block diagram) view of communications modulation and demodulation; (3) The MATLAB[®] simulation approach forces students to think about how to perform a proper simulation (e.g. set appropriate sampling rate, set appropriate specifications for digital filter design for envelope detector or discriminator, etc.) for both analog and digital simulation; and (4) The MATLAB[®] simulation approach sets a starting point for our students as they pursue software defined radio (SDR) communications applications in some of their senior design projects. We find synergy in combining the two pedagogical approaches in most of the labs in our communications systems course, and this typically results in enhanced student comprehension.

While more formal assessment will be conducted over the next two years, at this point we know from course feedback that students very much appreciate both learning tools. Students commonly remark that the TIMS[™] really highlights the “big picture,” and helps them understand what to expect before they start the MATLAB[®] simulations, while coding up the MATLAB[®] simulations gets them “into the weeds,” and gives them the tools to test out ideas that support their senior projects.

Keywords—*electrical engineering education, communication engineering education, student experiments*

I. INTRODUCTION

As faculty who teach undergraduate courses in the Electrical Engineering major, we routinely search for ways to enhance student learning and excitement for the subject matter. Sometimes students appreciate seeing simulations, while other times they appreciate experimentation, and the debate continues as to the appropriate mix in undergraduate education [1], [2].

Some researchers have commented [3] that a TIMS[™] based experimentation approach (in a very similar course as ours) garnered high marks for student satisfaction, and students acquired more skill and confidence in experimental methods. Our experiences are consistent with these observations. In our work, however, we suggest that a mix of simulation and experimentation has multiple advantages, and we take this approach in our senior-level undergraduate electrical engineering course called Communication Systems.

We see that an “experimental” TIMS[™] based approach [3] makes students feel that they are engaged in “real-world modulation and demodulation.” Furthermore, the very nature of the TIMS[™] based approach (where every TIMS[™] module has a specific function) [4] is a self-reinforcing “concept map” or block diagram view of the entire modulation/demodulation process.

We also see value in having our students do MATLAB[®] simulations, because such (digital) simulations force students to grapple with the details of setting up a proper simulation (e.g. setting appropriate sampling rate, using reasonable vector lengths for use in an FFT, design of an appropriate digital filter for use as a frequency discriminator, etc.) Since many of these same students are also learning about software defined radio (SDR) concepts for use in their senior projects, we see merit in our students understanding how to perform MATLAB[®] and Simulink[®] simulations.

We find synergy in combining the two pedagogical approaches in most of the labs in our communications systems course, and our experience suggests this results in enhanced student comprehension. Typical student comments are that the TIMS[™] experiments help to reinforce the concept maps for modulation/demodulation, and MATLAB[®] simulations force students to learn how to do proper simulations, while forcing them to recall information from previous courses.

Preliminary assessment suggests that students gain considerable insight from both the MATLAB[®] simulations and TIMS[™] experiments, however more formal assessment needs to be garnered over the next two years.

II. OVERVIEW OF OUR EQUIPMENT SUITE FOR COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS LAB

The primary equipment suite used for our Communication Systems labs is shown in Figure 1. Equipment listed from top to bottom include: EMONA TIMS-301, Agilent DSO 6034A Digitizing Oscilloscope, Agilent 89410A Vector Signal Analyzer, Agilent 33220A Function Generator, Rolls 35 Watt Stereo Power Amplifier, an AM/FM tuner, and stereo speakers. The general strategy for our labs is that students use low frequency sinusoidal and digital signals from the EMONA TIMS-301, and relatively narrow-band audio signals (demodulated audio) from the AM/FM tuner output, as message signals, as they study various modulation and demodulation methods in each lab. Labs using our primary equipment suite include Review of Fourier Series, Amplitude Modulation and Demodulation, Frequency Modulation and Demodulation, Pulse Code Modulation, and AM Single Sideband Modulation and Demodulation. Here we will focus on three labs: Amplitude Modulation/Demodulation, Frequency Modulation/Demodulation, and AM Single Sideband Modulation/Demodulation.

Fig. 1. Communication Systems laboratory primary equipment suite

In addition to the primary equipment suite, students have access to Windows 7.0 work stations where they are able to transfer data from the Agilent 89410A Vector Signal Analyzer to MATLAB[®] for later analyses. Students also have access to laboratory computers in order to perform the MATLAB[®] coding portion of each laboratory.

III. AMPLITUDE MODULATION (AM) AND DEMODULATION

This lab consists of several parts: (1) A MATLAB[®] study of AM generation, (2) a MATLAB[®] study of envelope detection, (3) a MATLAB[®] study of I & Q demodulation, (4) a TIMS[™] study of AM DSB-LC (large carrier), (5) a TIMS[™] study of AM DSB-SC (suppressed carrier), and (6) a TIMS[™] study of demodulation using product detection methods.

A. Studying AM using MATLAB[®]

Students are asked to write a short MATLAB[®] M-file which generates an AM (DSB-LC and DSB-SC) signal, with carrier frequency of 3kHz, a sinusoidal modulating frequency of 100Hz, a modulation index of 0.2 (for DSB-LC), and a sampling frequency of 50kHz. After successfully generating this signal and viewing it in both the time and frequency domains, they learn how their plots change as a function of modulation index and modulating frequency. They are also asked to consider why the sampling rate was chosen to be that value for purposes of simulation.

Students then use MATLAB[®] to demodulate the signals (using I&Q demodulation and envelope detection for the DSB-LC, and product detection for the DSB-SC.) They perform graphical comparisons of the original message and demodulated waveform, and draw conclusions based on their observations. Student feedback tells us that the MATLAB[®] simulations teach them a lot about how one can write code to perform simulations and test ideas.

B. Studying AM Using TIMS[™]

Students then use TIMS[™] to generate AM DSB-SC, using the audio oscillator as a (low frequency) sinusoidal message signal, and a 100kHz carrier. They use an analog multiplier on the TIMS[™] to generate the AM signal, and they view the DSB-SC signal at a center frequency of 100kHz in the frequency domain. They vary the amplitude and frequency of the low frequency sinusoidal message signal, and observe the effects in both time and frequency domains. At this point we have the students switch the message signal, from the low frequency sinusoidal message, to the (demodulated) audio signal coming out of the FM tuner, and they observe the DSB-SC signal in both the time and frequency domains.

Finally, we have the students demodulate that signal, by routing the DSB-SC signal to a “multiplier” module (which performs the function of a product detector), and then to a low pass filter module. The “multiplier module” multiplies the DSB-SC signal by a (variable) phase shifted carrier on the TIMS[™], and students learn about the importance of aligning the phase of the carrier and the local oscillator during product demodulation. The output of the “multiplier module” is sent through a low pass filter on the TIMS[™], and the output of the low pass filter is routed to the audio amplifier and speakers, so students are able to listen to their demodulated audio, while observing all signals in the time and frequency domains.

At this point, students begin adjusting the low pass filter bandwidth and gain, and begin shifting the phase of the local oscillator. Student feedback suggests that they very much appreciate the full sensory immersive experience of the

TIMS™ portion of this lab, as it helps them to remember important concepts.

IV. FREQUENCY MODULATION (FM) AND DEMODULATION

This lab consists of several parts: (1) A study of FM using the Agilent DSO 6034A Digitizing Oscilloscope, Agilent 89410A Vector Signal Analyzer, and the Agilent 33220A Function Generator, (2) a MATLAB® investigation of FM demodulation from I & Q data, (3) a MATLAB® generation of FM and demodulation via a frequency discriminator, and (4) a TIMS™ investigation of FM modulation and demodulation using Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) demodulation and frequency discriminator demodulation methods. Here we will focus on parts (2)-(4).

A. Studying FM using MATLAB®

After students study FM signals in both time and frequency domains using a signal generator, oscilloscope, and dynamic signal analyzer, they learn about three methods for FM demodulation: (1) Demodulation from base band In-Phase and Quadrature (I&Q) data, (2) Demodulation using a phase-locked loop (PLL), and (3) Demodulation using frequency discriminator techniques.

For FM demodulation from I&Q data, we ask students to turn to MATLAB® for additional insight. We provide them a MATLAB® data file (.mat file) that is a “baseband” I&Q signal (commonly referred to as a “complex envelope” for the FM signal), sampled at 25kHz, and we ask them to demodulate and play the resulting audio file.

As we present in class, if one is presented with “base band” in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) data, a classic way to perform FM demodulation is to perform operations on the vector $I+jQ$. We tell our students since FM is a form of “angle modulation,” it seems logical to examine the angle of the vector $I+jQ$ in order to begin demodulation. We ask students to develop a simple function in MATLAB® which will perform the desired demodulation. Recognizing the “angle” function provides a return argument from $-\pi$ to π , we ask them to consider “unwrapping” the angle of the $I+jQ$ vector to avoid discontinuities. Finally, we remind them that they are not interested specifically in the “angle” of $I+jQ$ (in radians), but more interested in changes in that angle as a function of time (instantaneous frequency – radians/sec). After some thought (and considerable coaching), they come up with a single line of code that accomplishes the desired demodulations: $y=\text{diff}(\text{unwrap}(\text{angle}(S)))$, where S represents the baseband $I+jQ$ vector. At that point they use the MATLAB® commands “sound” or “audioplayer” to listen to the message, and they usually take some time to think about why that methodology worked so well! Student feedback on this part of the lab is tremendous.

In addition, we have our students generate an FM signal with carrier frequency 5kHz, modulating frequency 100Hz, a modulation index of 1.0, with sampling frequency 22050Hz. That signal is then used as the FM signal input to a frequency discriminator (that they must design!), and the simulation is accomplished completely in MATLAB®. This portion of the lab requires that they remember something about digital filter

design (studied in earlier courses), and it requires that they design the filter such that the frequency of interest is in the center of the transition band of the filter they design. Students were less than enthusiastic in their feedback for this part of the lab!

B. Studying FM using TIMS™

For this module, students use the Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO) module on TIMS™ to generate an FM signal at a 100kHz center frequency. Both the center frequency and the frequency deviation (VCO “gain”) can be adjusted on the VCO card. The “message input” to the VCO is taken from the demodulated audio from the FM tuner at the bottom of the equipment suite (from Figure 1), and we have the students generate a relatively narrow band FM signal (small modulation index). After students view the FM signal in both the time and frequency domains, we give them the assignment: demodulate that signal by building a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) detector, and play the demodulated audio through the stereo amplifier and speakers.

At this point, students are initially confused, and I refer them to a standard block diagram for a PLL detector (Figure 2). We tell them that each block of the PLL diagram consists of one or two modules from the set of TIMS™ modules, and they then begin to build their PLL. We explain that the phase detector is implemented as a multiplier cascaded with a low pass filter, and the input to the PLL is the FM signal they just created.

Fig. 2. Basic block diagram of phase-locked loop (PLL) for FM demodulation.

To assist them in getting a working PLL, we advise them to follow these steps: (1) Make sure the VCO in the feedback path of the PLL is set to the same frequency as the center frequency of the incoming signal, (2) set the “gain” of the VCO in the PLL feedback path at roughly the same “gain” as the VCO that is generating the FM (relatively low), (3) make the low pass filter relatively wide in the feed-forward path of the PLL, and (4) lower the gain of the gain block in the feed forward path. At this point we explain to students that the input to the VCO block is the demodulated audio of interest, and we are interested in listening to that signal.

By slowly adjusting the VCO gain and the bandwidth of the low pass filter, students are usually able to get their PLL’s working perfectly within 15-20 minutes, and they feel such a sense of accomplishment when they can hear the demodulated audio output. Furthermore, they are always amazed to hear how perfect the demodulated audio sounds. At this point we have a “teachable moment,” and we ask our students to make the PLL “break lock” by (1) reducing the VCO gain or low

pass filter gain, (2) reducing the bandwidth of the low pass filter, or (3) changing the frequency of the VCO in the feedback path. By the end of the lab, students have obtained considerable insight into the workings of a PLL, and it is at that point we draw parallels for them between concepts they have seen in Computer Controls class (e.g. P, PD, PID controllers) and PLL demodulation. Feedback on this part of the lab is overwhelmingly positive, and students remark that they gained tremendous insight into PLL theory and operations from this lab experience. Assessment data taken from their FM lab reports and hourly exams also suggest that students have a more solid understanding of PLL concepts.

Finally, students disconnect their PLL TIMS™ configurations, and reconfigure the VCO that generates the original FM signal to a center frequency of 70kHz. Students then use the 60kHz low pass filter module from TIMS™ to implement a “frequency discriminator.” Since the center frequency of the FM signal now lies in the transition band of their low pass filter, they are generating a signal that varies in amplitude and frequency. By passing this signal to the “utilities module” (which has an envelope detector), students learn that they have performed FM detection by performing envelope detection on an “AM-like” signal. Again, they listen to the demodulated audio output, and again they are impressed at the audio quality.

V. AM SINGLE SIDEBAND GENERATION AND DEMODULATION

This lab consists of two parts: (1) A MATLAB® study of single sideband (SSB) amplitude modulation and demodulation, and (2) a TIMS™ investigation of single sideband amplitude modulation and demodulation.

A. Studying AM-SSB using MATLAB®

During the AM lab, students wrote MATLAB® code to generate an AM DSB-SC signal with a carrier frequency of 3kHz, and a sinusoidal message signal of 100Hz. Here they modify their code to produce the AM-SSB signal, either upper (“-”) or lower (“+”) side band, by using the equation

$$s(t) = A_c [m(t)\cos(\omega_c t) \mp \hat{m}(t)\sin(\omega_c t)] \quad (1)$$

where A_c is a scaling factor, $m(t)$ is the message, and $\hat{m}(t)$ is defined as the Hilbert transform of the message. Students write their own “Hilbert transformer” by using the “fft” function, multiplying positive frequency components by “-j” and negative frequency components by “j”, and then inverse transforming the result by calling the “ifft” routine. Using a sinusoidal signal for $m(t)$, students see that they can elect to generate either the upper or lower sideband signal by changing the sign on $\hat{m}(t)$ from equation (1). Students also see that they can multiply the SSB signal by a (coherent) carrier signal, low pass filter, and retrieve the original sinusoidal message.

B. Studying AM-SSB using TIMS™

Using the TIMS™ modules (specifically the 100kHz sine/cosine waveform generators, the audio signal generator, and the quadrature phase shifter module), students generate an

AM-SSB (lower) signal at 100kHz using the Hilbert transform or “phasing method” discussed in class. Using the audio signal generator as the $m(t)$ initially, students view the SSB signal in both the time and frequency domains. After students are convinced that their phasing method is working, they use the audio signal from the FM tuner in the primary equipment suite, and view the results in both the time and frequency domains. At this point, students are impressed that this “phasing method” works so well in completely eliminating one of the sidebands. They finish the lab by using a product detector (with oscillator that is coherent with the carrier) in order to demodulate the AM-SSB signal. They route the signal output to the amplifier and speakers, and enjoy the resulting music.

Feedback from this portion of the lab suggests that our students appreciated both the MATLAB® and TIMS™ sections of the lab, and assessment results from lab submissions and exams suggests to us that student comprehension of AM-SSB concepts has improved over the last several years.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We presented some of the ways we have combined MATLAB® based simulation with Telecommunications Instructional Modeling (Emona-TIMS™) experimental methods to enhance student learning in a senior-level communications systems laboratory at the U.S. Coast Guard Academy. While relative merits of simulation versus experimentation have been debated over the years, our experience suggests that students very much appreciate that the TIMS™ based approach inherently reinforces a “concept map” (block diagram) view of communications modulation and demodulation. Furthermore, they also see value in doing MATLAB® simulation, because they see it as a first step towards testing senior project research ideas, and they see value in learning how to perform a proper simulation. Although we are in the early stages of assessment, we do see advantages in combining these two pedagogical approaches, based on student feedback and improved student comprehension.

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